

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE 2 – GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D4.1: Report on plant/bacteria consortia efficiency for the removal of metal ions from wastewater

REPORTING PERIOD	
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List of Deliverables

D. No	Name	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)
D 4.1	Report on plant/bacteria consortia efficiency for the removal of metal ions from wastewaters	REPORT	PU	M24		09/04/2025
D 4.2	Report on the adsorption performances of porous solids derived from biomasses valorization and non-recyclable plastic wastes	REPORT	PU	M24		09/04/2025

CONTENTS

The Deliverable is divided in two parallel activities: Development of plant/bacteria from wastewater and treatment of dairy wastewater. The two processes found an overlap with the exchange of input/output materials for a combined wastewater treatment.

A) INTRODUCTION

Bacterial isolates, screened for their plant growth promoting (PGP) traits and for their tolerance to abiotic stresses (especially metals) (Song et al. 2021), can be used for water assisted-phytoremediation together with accumulating/hyperaccumulating plants to build an efficient contaminant-removal system (Raklami et al. 2022). The best selection of plant-microbe consortia is crucial to obtain good results for improving the contaminant-removal efficiency, especially in large industrial scale (Sharma, 2021).

B) ROLE OF PARTNERS

Recovery of metals in wastewater by means of accumulating/hyperaccumulating plants even enhanced by microbial consortia, to develop the best growth conditions to recover metals from plant organs.

C) EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

Different bacterial strains, previously isolated and characterized for their PGP capabilities, were tested for their tolerance to different metals as reported below (Table 1).

Metal	Bacterium	MIC by broth micro-dilution
Ni	SVB6R1	18.75 mM
	Pf7	18.75 mM
	RA4	18.75 mM
	SP2	18.75 mM
Cd	SVB6R1	2.34 mM
	Pf7	9.37 mM
	RA4	4.68 mM
	SP2	4.68 mM
Pb	SVB6R1	37.5 mM
	Pf7	37.5 mM
	RA4	37.5 mM
	SP2	37.5 mM
Cu	SVB6R1	18.75 mM
	Pf7	37.5 mM
	RA4	37.5 mM
	SP2	9.37 mM
Zn	SVB6R1	4.68 mM
	Pf7	37.5 mM
	RA4	37.5 mM
	SP2	37.5 mM
Cr	SVB6R1	0.58 mM
	Pf7	2.34 mM
	RA4	2.34 mM
	SP2	2.34 mM

Table 1. MIC values for metals obtained in each bacterium. The table shows the MICs of metals in the different used bacteria. *Cd*: cadmium; *Cu*: copper; *Cr*: chromium; *Ni*: nickel; *Pb*: lead; *Zn*: zinc. SVB6R1: *P. brassicacearum*; Pf7: *P. protegens*; RA4: *R. aquatilis*; SP2: *S. plymuthica*.

To verify the compatibility between microbes and plants, a monocot (*Sorghum bicolor* L.) and a dicot (*Pisum sativum*) Angiosperm species were chosen. Although the germination percentage was significantly affected by the different treatments (Figure 1A and 2A) both in *S. bicolor* and *P. sativum*, the root length was influenced by the microbe presence only in dicot species (Figure 1B and 2B).

Figure 1. The figure shows the mean values and the relative standard errors of the germination percentage (A) and the root length (B) in *S. bicolor* seeds inoculated or not with bacteria after 72 h of incubation. **Control:** uninoculated plants; **SVB6R1:** plants inoculated with *P. brassicacearum*; **Pf7:** plants inoculated with *P. protegens*; **RA4:** plants inoculated with *R. aquatilis*; **SP2:** plants inoculated with *S. plymuthica*. Different letters between treatments express statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 2. The figure shows the mean values and the relative standard errors of the germination percentage (A) and the root length (B) in *S. bicolor* seeds inoculated or not with bacteria after 72 h of incubation. **Control:** uninoculated plants; **SVB6R1:** plants inoculated with *P. brassicacearum*; **Pf7:** plants inoculated with *P. protegens*; **RA4:** plants inoculated with *R. aquatilis*; **SP2:** plants inoculated with *S. plymuthica*. Different letters between treatments express statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

The bacteria were also tested for their growth compatibility (Table 2) to verify if a consortium could also be used on plants.

Table 2. Bacterial growth compatibilities (TSA plate).

Strain	Pf7	SVB6R1	RA4	SP2
Pf7				
SVB6R1	+			
RA4	+	+		
SP2	+	+	+	+

+: compatible; -: incompatible; nc: not clear. SVB6R1: *P. brassicacearum*; Pf7: *P. protegens*; RA4: *R. aquatilis*; SP2: *S. plymuthica*.

The assays showed no signs of inhibition were reported on Petri dishes; therefore all the bacteria can be used together in a single formulation. For this reason, *in vitro* germination tests were employed to verify the effect of this bacterial mix on the same monocot and dicot species used before (Figure 3 and 4). The considered parameters were negatively influenced by the used inoculum both in *S. bicolor* (Figure 3) and *P. sativum* (Figure 4). Based on these results we chosen to proceed the experimentation inoculating a single strain in the growth substrate of the selected plants.

Figure 3. The figure shows the mean values and the relative standard errors of the germination percentage (A) and the root length (B) in *S. bicolor* seeds inoculated or not with the bacterial consortium after 72 h of incubation. **Control:** uninoculated; **Mix:** plants inoculated with *P. brassicacearum*, *P. protegens*, *R. aquatilis*, *S. plymuthica*. Different letters between treatments express statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 4. The figure shows the mean values and the relative standard errors of the germination percentage (A) and the root length (B) in *P. sativum* seeds inoculated or not with the bacterial consortium after 72 h of incubation. **Control:** uninoculated; **Mix:** plants inoculated with *P. brassicacearum*, *P. protegens*, *R. aquatilis*, *S. plymuthica*. Different letters between treatments express statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

According to the certified method UNICHIM n° 1651 (2003) 2007, phytotoxicity test was performed on *S. bicolor* and *P. sativum* on different metal polluted waters to assess the most tolerant Angiosperm.

As observed in the following graphs (Figure 5A, B and Figure 6A, B), the two Angiosperm species had an opposite behavior, underlying that monocot species performed better than dicot one.

Germination assay (*Sorghum bicolor*)

Figure 5. The figure shows the mean values and the relative standard errors of the germination percentage (A) and the root length (B) in *S. bicolor* seeds treated with contaminated waters after 72 h of incubation. C: unpolluted water; W1, W2, W3, W4: different contaminated waters. Different letters between treatments express statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

Germination assay (*Sorghum bicolor*)

Figure 6. The figure shows the mean values and the relative standard errors of the germination percentage (A) and the root length (B) in *P. sativum* seeds treated with contaminated waters after 72 h of incubation. C: unpolluted water; W1, W2, W3, W4: different contaminated waters. Different letters between treatments express statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

Based on the obtained results, single bacterial strains will be utilized in combination with a monocot plant species. As reported in the literature, one of the most monocot hyperaccumulating

macrophyte (*Phragmites australis*) for water decontamination purposes will be used. Moreover, according to the selectivity and efficiency of metal removal, plant-microbe-based optimized approaches will be extended to the partners of UNITO to further implement the system efficiency adding microalgae to the experimentation.

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[UNIPV MAGNI]

Valorization of dairy wastewater by an engineered microorganism

Background

The valorization process includes an optimized bacterial strain that is able to convert lactose from concentrated whey permeate (CWP) into ethanol at high level. The fermentation process requires specific temperature and pH, and results in an ethanol titer in the 50-60 g/L range in about 3 days (**Figure 1**). At the end of the fermentation process, the bacterial biomass is separated by filtration and ethanol is extracted via distillation. The residual ethanol-free liquid obtained by distillation represents the main waste of the process.

We previously evaluated the pollutant load of this waste by measuring total dry matter (TDM) and chemical oxygen demand (COD). Our currently available strain is able to reduce both TSS and COD compared to the initial CWP and compared to fermentations by other previously available strains (**Figure 2**). However, the COD value is still too high and residual liquid disposal is still unfeasible. For this reason, the activities below have been performed to lower the costs of the process and expand the possibilities of valorizing the input and the output of our process.

Figure 1. Time course of sugars (lactose + glucose + galactose) and ethanol in different wastewaters from two industrial sources (CWP and CWP_R).

Strain	TDM (g/L)	TSS (g/L)	DM (g/L)	COD (gO ₂ /L)
CWP ₁₃₀ ^b	141.57 ^b	- ^c	-	126.6
W-pL13	60.65 (0.50)	4.89 (0.38)	55.76 (0.12)	42.91 (1.61)
W _{ΔLFP} -pL13	51.05 (0.98)	4.53 (0.08)	46.52 (0.09)	35.07 (5.50)

Figure 2. Total dry matter (TDM), total suspended solids (TSS), dry matter (DM) and chemical oxygen demand (COD) after fermentation, biomass separation and distillation. CWP130 is a wastewater with about 13% dry matter mainly represented by lactose. W-pL13 and W_{ΔLFP}-pL13 are two ethanologenic strains previously constructed in the lab. b, one measurement available, which was consistent with previous data; c, not measured.

Fermentation experiments to generate residual waste liquid to test microalgae growth

Laboratory-scale fermentations (0.6 L), biomass separation and distillation were run to obtain different batches of residual waste. This residual liquid and the initial CWP are being tested for microalgae growth (with Alberta Pinnola, UniPV-DBB), to find the most promising wastewater that could be used to generate algal biomass. Since the used microalgae are not able to consume lactose, growth can be performed upstream and downstream of fermentation, to best valorize the available residuals.

Characterization of input, output and strain

Different analyses were carried out to improve our knowledge on the input wastewater (measuring possible inhibitors and nitrogen sources), and on the distillation residual (measuring the residual compounds – sugars, alcohols, COD, and investigating its pollutant load), see **Figure 3** and **Figure 4**.

These analyses elucidated important details, e.g., CWP contains nitrogen sources that are poorly bioavailable and could be targeted in the future to improve bacterial fermentation performance.

Nutritional values	U.M.	Result	Uncertainty
Energy	kJ / 100 g	224	
Energy	kcal / 100 g	53	
Total fats (by hydrolysis)	g / 100 g	<0.10	
Carbohydrates	g / 100 g	12.6	
Total sugars	g / 100 g	12.0	
Dietary fiber	g / 100 g	<0.10	
Proteins (Nx6.25)	g / 100 g	0.600	+/- 0.068
Salt (Sodium x 2.5)	g / 100 g	0.368	

Other nutritional analysis	U.M.	Result	Uncertainty
Sodium (Na)	mg / kg	1470	
Ash	g / 100 g	1.467	+/- 0.088
Moisture	g / 100 g	85.3	+/- 1.6

Acidic composition	U.M.	Result
Butyric acid (C4:0)	%	n.a.
Caproic acid (C6:0)	%	n.a.

Metals	U.M.	Result
Arsenic (As)	mg / kg	<0.004 (LOD)
Cadmium (Cd)	mg / kg	<0.004 (LOD)
Mercury (Hg)	mg / kg	<0.004 (LOD)
Lead (Pb)	mg / kg	<0.004 (LOD)

Other analyzed parameters	U.M.	Result
Fluoride	mg / kg	<0.40 (LOD)

Sugars	g/100g	Result	Uncertainty
Fructose	g/100g	<0.10	
Glucose	g/100g	<0.10	
Sucrose	g/100g	<0.10	
Maltose	g/100g	<0.50	
Lactose	g/100g	11.97	+/- 0.96

Figure 3. Analysis of CWP (input).

Parameter	U. M.	Result	Hazard Class Codes and Category R.1272/08 e s.m.i.	Hazard Indications	Limit	Hazard Characteristics	Method of Analysis
SPECIFIC WEIGHT	kg/l	1.01					CNR IRSA QD. 64 Vol.2 Met.3
RESIDUE 105°C	%	4.32					UNI EN 14346A
pH		5.3					CNR IRSA QD. 64 Vol.3 Met.1
COD	mg/kg	108000					APAT IRSA - CNR RAPPORT 29/03

BOD ₅ 99	mg/kg	65000					Vol.2 Met.5130
SEDIMENTABLE SOLIDS	ml/l	44					CNR IRSA QD. 64 Vol.2 Met.7
TOTAL SUSPENDED SOLIDS	mg/kg	34000					CNR IRSA QD. 64 Vol.2 Met.14
SOLUBLE AMMONIA	mg/kg	< 10	Skin Corr. 1B, Aquatic Acute 1	H314, H400	50000, 250000	HP 8, HP 14	
ALUMINUM	mg/kg	2.1					EPA 6010C
ARSENIC	mg/kg	< 1	Acute Tox. 3, Aquatic Chronic 1	H301, H410	500, 2500	HP 6, HP 14	EPA 6010C
BARIUM	mg/kg	1.2	Water-react. 2	H261	2500, 25000	HP 3	EPA 6010C

BORON	mg/kg	4.4					EPA 6010C
CADMIUM	mg/kg	< 1	Pyr. Sol. 1, Acute Tox. 2, STOT RE 1, Aquatic Acute 1	H330, H372, H400	100, 2500	HP 7, HP 14	EPA 6010C
CHROMIUM	mg/kg	< 1					EPA 6010C
CHROMIUM VI COMPOUNDS	mg/kg	< 0.1	Carc. 1B, Aquatic Chronic 1	H350i, H410	1000, 2500	HP 7, HP 14	
IRON	mg/kg	4.7					EPA 6010C

PHOSPHORUS	mg/kg	1100	Flam. Sol. 1, Aquatic Chronic 3	H228, H412	250000	HP 3, HP 14	EPA 6010C
MANGANESE	mg/kg	1.1					EPA 6010C
MERCURY	mg/kg	< 1	Repr. 1B, Acute Tox. 2, STOT RE 1, Aquatic Chronic 1	H360D, H330, H372, H410	50, 500	HP 6, HP 14	EPA 6010C
NICKEL	mg/kg	< 1	Skin Sens. 1, Carc. 2, Aquatic Chronic 1	H317, H351, H410	1000, 2500	HP 6, HP 14	EPA 6010C
LEAD COMPOUNDS	mg/kg	< 1	Repr. 1A, Acute Tox. 4, STOT RE 2, Aquatic Chronic 1	H360Df, H302, H373, H410	100, 2500	HP 6, HP 14	EPA 6010C
COPPER	mg/kg	1.3	Flam. Liq. 3	H226	250000	HP 3	EPA 6010C
SOLUBLE COPPER AS SALTS	mg/kg	1.3					EPA 6010C
SELENIUM	mg/kg	< 1					EPA 6010C
TIN	mg/kg	< 1					EPA 6010C
ZINC	mg/kg	1.1					EPA 6010C
PHENOLS AS PHENOL	mg/kg	< 0.1	Muta. 2, Acute Tox. 3, Skin Corr. 1B	H341, H301, H314	1000, 5000	HP 6, HP 8	R. P. Met. C13
TKN KJELDAHL NITROGEN	mg/kg	50					APAT IRSA - CNR RAPPORT 29/03

HYDROCARBONS >C10	mg/kg	10	Carc. 1B, Muta. 2, Aquatic Chronic 2	H350, H341, H411	1000, 2500	HP 7, HP 14	UNI EN 14039
TOTAL OILS	mg/kg	800					CNR IRSA QD. 64 Vol.3 Met.4
SPECIFIC ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY	µS/cm	10000					APAT IRSA - CNR RAPPORT 29/03

ANIONIC SURFACTANTS	mg/kg	< 1					APAT IRSA - CNR RAPPORT 29/03
NON-IONIC SURFACTANTS	mg/kg	< 1					UNI 10511- 1+A1
AROMATIC SOLVENTS	mg/kg	< 10					EPA 8015C
HALOGENATED SOLVENTS	mg/kg	< 10					EPA 8015C
OTHER SOLVENTS							

Figure 4. Analysis of fermentation wastewater (output), before bacterial separation and distillation.

Analyses were also performed and on the bacterial strain by whole-genome sequencing, to characterize its stability, the mutations occurred during adaptive evolution that are associated with ethanol tolerance, and to assess the functionality of other sugar consumption pathways that could be useful for other valorization processes.

Scale-up & scale-down

To optimize the conditions for ethanol production, we evaluated design modifications to our demonstration plant (in the 50-100 L scale), installed in the Biotransformation Lab, that is currently able to support fermentation but at lower yield than lab-scale experiments (**Figure 5**). We discussed the modifications with FilterFlo S.r.l. that is currently implementing them.

Figure 5. Different ethanol production between fermentation experiments in a laboratory bioreactor (lab-scale) and a demonstration plant (scale-up).

In addition, to reproduce possible failures occurring during fermentation processes, a parallelized platform has been developed to carry out a scale-down using low-cost bioreactors (Chi.Bio) able to support bacterial growth continuously for long periods. The setup is currently working and additional bioreactor units will be available soon to enable investigations in five parallel reactors, aimed at finding optimal conditions (e.g., inoculum size, supplements, emulation of events, e.g., temperature shifts, base addition spikes, oxygen availability) to eventually enhance robustness and decrease costs.